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Student Comparative Self-Assessment based on Learning Outcomes

Evaluation of a Stand-Alone Course on Sustainability and Engineering.

André Baier

Lecturer

Technische Universität Berlin

Berlin, Germany

Andre.Baier@tu-berlin.de

ABSTRACT

The on-going evaluation of a stand-alone on sustainability and responsibility at Technische Universität Berlin aims at a comprehensive triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data. This paper will present the core of the quantitative evaluation: A student comparative self-assessment. The students themselves rate their competences on a 6-point Likert scale. The items of this survey are based on the learning outcomes of the course. The assessment takes place either at the beginning (pre) and at the end (post) of the course or as a combined assessment looking back to the beginning of the course (then) and after completing the course (post). The pre-/then-/post-testing results show a significant gain of competences. The described process can easily be adapted which makes this paper relevant for anybody interested in evaluating a course on sustainability and engineering.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability, Ethics or Engineering Education Research

Keywords: self-assessment, competences, sustainability, ethics, learning outcomes

INTRODUCTION

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) aims at fostering a generation of active citizens equipped with the tools, knowledge, and experience they will require to induce sustainable changes in both professional and personal contexts [1]. ESD is unique in its quest to ensure graduates to not simply graduate with more knowledge, but newfound competences to embody the traits they value and the capability to act accordingly. In order to be effective within an outcome-based education, competences need to be implemented as learning outcomes. Next, these learning outcomes should be aligned with teaching/learning activities, assessment of students and course evaluation to ensure a coherent teaching/learning experience.

The Blue Engineering Course at Technische Universität Berlin (TUB) addresses the ecological and social responsibility of engineers. Its learning outcomes are based on the concept of Gestaltungskompetenz [1]. Therefore, the learning activities are organized in such a manner that students may acquire competences of an ESD. An effective evaluation of such a course is demanding due to the complex nature of ESD competences and the corresponding activities. This paper will provide a case study on how to describe learning outcomes for such a course and how to evaluate whether the students reach these learning outcomes through a student comparative self-assessment.

1 DESIGN AND CONDUCTION OF THE BLUE ENGINEERING COURSE

The Blue Engineering Course is organized in a highly interactive manner that takes the shift from teaching to learning [2] seriously. Roughly speaking, only one third of the course is conducted by the tutors while two thirds are conducted by the participants themselves. For a successful completion of this 6 ECTS course, the students have to fulfill four assignments: 1) to keep a learning journal [3] over the whole semester; 2) to conduct an existing teaching/learning unit of about 60 minutes length; 3) to develop and conduct a new demanding teaching/learning unit on a topic of their choosing [4]; 4) to document this teaching/learning unit in such a way as to enable others to conduct it.

The fourteen-week course has been first conducted during the winter-semester 2011/2012 with 24 students. From this semester onward, it has been offered every semester, which amounts to a total of 12 semesters and 564 students who participated in it. The number of participants was raised continuously and levels now over last six semesters at about 70 students per semesters. About 31% of the participants study mechanical engineering and about 22% study industrial engineering, where the course can be chosen as an option from a list of compulsory courses. The rest of the students take it as an elective from various study programmes crossing all faculties.

2 LEARNING OUTCOMES OF THE BLUE ENGINEERING COURSE

The description of the learning outcomes of the course follows a design down process, which means that the learning outcomes on the higher educational levels function as guidance on the lower levels [5]. State law as well as various regulations at TUB require that students will learn about responsibility as well as sustainability through various study programmes. Therefore, the described course can easily be integrated into the overall learning outcomes of said university.

For the course itself, two learning outcomes describe what the participants will have learned at the end of the course. These two learning outcomes on the general level of the course are then further 'designed down' to be used on lesson level as well as on exercise level. The learning outcomes on the various level have been developed in an open participatory process over the course of five years. The multi-disciplined core team consisted of the professor responsible for the course, two lecturers charged with the further development of the course, 8 tutors and many members of the student group that has initially developed the course. Their work was regularly feedbacked by their peers and participants of the course.

2.1 Two Learning Outcomes on the General Level

The two general learning outcomes consider for the individual responsibility as well as the collective responsibility of (future) engineers [6]. Furthermore, the learning outcomes

identifies engineers as relevant actors in the democratisation of society nature-relations [7] as well as the general power relations of society [8].

1) The prospective engineers analyze and evaluate the present reciprocal relations of technology, individuals, nature and society by taking different perspectives. Based on this analysis and evaluation, they are able to state their personal perspective and values of the reciprocal relations and act accordingly.

2) The prospective engineers cooperate with others to analyze and evaluate in a democratic process the present reciprocal relations of technology, individuals, nature and society. Based on their analysis and evaluation, they are able to work out a collective understanding with regard to their collective values and democratise the reciprocal relations.

2.2 Twelve Learning Outcomes on Course and Lesson Level

These two general learning outcomes are further design downed by adapting an existing framework of competences of ESD. The concept of Gestaltungskompetenz [1] was chosen over other concepts as it is the only concept that is placed within the broader framework of the set of OECD key competences. It comes with many good practice implementations as it is widely used within Germany where it was used to implement the UNESCO Decade of ESD [1] at the secondary school level. In addition, it is also picked up on an international level in higher education where a trend towards a harmonization of ESD competences is identified [9].

For the design down process, the 12 broadly recognized sub-competences of Gestaltungskompetenz of an ESD [1] have been reformulated as learning outcomes. Next, they were adapted to reflect the two general learning outcomes which led to a total of 12 specific learning outcomes for the Blue Engineering course. See Table 1. These learning outcomes are already specific enough to constructively align with the broad range of learning activities of the course as well as with the formative assessment of the students. Furthermore, this precisioning allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the whole course as described in this paper.

3 EVALUATION OF THE ANONYMOUS COURSE

The Anonymous Course is part of an ESD. As such, it provides a highly demanding and complex learning environment where students have to define and solve problems themselves. Therefore, it does not aim at simple competences that can be assessed in laboratory-like settings where the learning outcome is reached if students would answer, react or behave in one specific way alone and in that way only [5]. If the learning outcomes of a course are competences of an ESD neither one summative assessment, i.e. a multiple-choice test at the end, of the students seems applicable nor one summative assessment. Instead, a comprehensive triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data is necessary to ensure that all aspects of the learning outcomes and therefore all aspects of the 12 sub-competences of Gestaltungskompetenz are properly evaluated. For example, the qualitative evaluation is realized through the analysis of the learning journals as well as through written feedback at the end of particular lessons and at the end of the course. Among other data acquisitions, a quantitative evaluation is realized through standardised questionnaires for the whole course which is the same for all courses on faculty level as well as the evaluation of particular lessons through questionnaires that are specific to this lesson. In addition, there are two mixed evaluations that are also specific to certain lessons of the Anonymous Course.

Table 1. Gestaltungskompetenz / Learning Outcomes / Questions for Self-Assessment

Sub-Competences of Gestaltungskompetenz (de Haan 2010)	Learning Outcomes of the Anonymous Course on Course Level	Questions for Student Self-Assessment
OECD - Competence Category - Tools - Using Tools Interactively		
T1 - Perspective-Taking - to gather knowledge in a spirit of openness to the world, integrating new perspectives	T1 - Students take perspectives, change points of view and gather diverse forms of knowledge (i.e. scientific, traditional, common sense) from various actors on the spatial and temporal effects of technology on individuals, society and nature.	T1.1 - argue from different points of view T1.2 - describe the influence of technology on nature and society
T2 - Anticipation - to think and act in a forward-looking manner	T2 - Students anticipate spatial and temporal effects of technology on individuals, society and nature.	T2.1 - consider present and future effects of one's own actions T2.2 - describe the local and global effects of technology
T3 - Gaining Interdisciplinary Knowledge - to acquire knowledge and to act in an interdisciplinary manner	T3 - Students gain knowledge of the reciprocal relations between technology, individuals, nature and society through inter- and transdisciplinary approaches.	T3.1 - find and incorporate knowledge outside of my own discipline
T4 - Deal with Incomplete and Overcomplex Informations - to deal with incomplete and overly complex information	T4 - Students deal with incomplete and over complex information on the reciprocal relations between technology, individuals, nature and society and the risks, dangers and uncertainties which arise from them.	T4.1 - choose an option, although possible consequences are unknown
OECD - Competence Category - Cooperation - Interacting in Heterogeneous Groups		
C1 - Cooperation - to co-operate in decision-making processes	C1 - Students cooperate for a democratic decision-making with regard to process, result and implementation.	C1.1 - reflect upon a group process with respect to process and result
C2- Cope with Dilemmas of Decision-Making - to cope with individual dilemmatic situation of decision-making	C2 - Students cope with dilemmas of decision-making when values and aims are conflicting.	C2.1 - mediate conflicts of goals and values with others

C3 - Participation - to participate in collective decision-making processes	C3 - Students participate at collective decision-making processes.	C3.1 - constructively introduce my point of view in a group discussion
C4 - Motivation - to motivate oneself as well as others to become active	C4 - Students motivate oneself and others to democratize the reciprocal relations between technology, individuals, nature and society.	C4.1 - spread knowledge towards other students C4.2 - prepare a didactical unit on a complex topic
OECD - Competence Category - Action - Acting Autonomously		
A1 - Reflect Principles - to reflect upon one's own principles and those of others	A1 - Students reflect principles which control the reciprocal relations of technology, individuals, nature and society.	A1.1 - know one's own attitude and values towards technology A1.2 - put oneself in the position of others to understand their motives
A2 - Act Morally - to refer to the idea of equity in decision-making and planning actions	A2 - Students identify the underlying values which shape the reciprocal relations of technology, nature, individuals and society and to use them to act morally.	A2.1 - act according to one's own attitudes and values
A3 - Act Independently - to plan and act autonomously	A3 - Students plan independently and act autonomously according to one's own values.	A3.1 - prepare one's own problem statement
A4 - Support Others - to show empathy for and solidarity with the disadvantaged	A4 - Students support others who are disadvantaged due to the dominating design of the reciprocal relations between technology, individuals, nature and society.	A4.1 - identify causes of social inequalities

4 STUDENT COMPARATIVE SELF-ASSESSMENT SURVEY

4.1 Design of the Student Comparative Self-Assessment Survey

A student comparative self-assessment survey is the central part of the quantitative evaluation. For this, each of the 12 specific learning outcomes has been reformulated to reflect a specific part of the course. See Table 1. In addition, to the listed items which were evaluated in every semester, there was a varying set of questions which were used in specific semesters alone. Each item was to be answered on a 6-Point Likert-Scale where students could rate their own competences ranging from 'high' to 'low'. The data collection took place as a classical comparative survey where the students self-assess their competences at two different points in time. In total, five consecutive semesters have been

evaluated in this manner from winter-semester 2014/2015 up until the winter-semester 2016/2017. In the first three semesters the surveys were conducted in a pre-post manner, meaning that the survey was filled out in the very first lesson (pre) as well as in the very last lesson of the course (post). For the past two semesters the same items were put into a then-post survey which was filled out at the end of the course. For this, the participants were asked to recall how competent they would judge themselves at the beginning of the course (then) and to judge how competent they are now at the end of the course (post).

4.2 Results of the Student Comparative Self-Assessment Survey

Table 2 shows the major results of the student comparative self-assessment survey. In total, 354 students have successfully completed the Anonymous course in the five evaluated semesters. However, only 216 students have completed the survey at the end of the class, which equals 61%. This discrepancy is due to the fact that the participation in the survey was totally voluntary and that the attendance at the course is generally lower at the end of the semester as students start to prepare for their exams.

Overall, the students judge all of the tested competences much higher at the end of the course than at the beginning of the course. Figure 1 shows the aggregated answers of the pre/then and post survey in a heat map. In addition, this finding is backed up with t-test results usually below $p = 0.01$ which would indicate a significant change. It has to be noted, that the then-post surveys do not show as strong positive gains in self-assessed competences as the pre-post surveys. However, this is in line with other research which stresses the point that then-post surveys might stronger be affected by the impact of implicit theories of change [10]. These quantitative results can also be verified through the qualitative evaluation.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper argues for the adaption of an existing set of ESD competences in a design down process in order to render them useful in a concrete course setting. It further shows how these specific competences can be implemented as learning outcomes. Course specific learning outcomes proved to be helpful for the design of aligned teaching/learning activities and corresponding assessments of students. In addition, specific learning outcomes that are based on competences can also be used for the evaluation of the course itself which may help to reveal if students judge themselves more competent after attending the course.

The workload of the lecturers can further be reduced by conducting the self-evaluation as a then-/post-survey as this type of survey requires only one survey at the end. This method does not endanger the comparative self-evaluation as it also may reveal significant competence gains on the side of the students.

The description of the learning outcomes for the Blue Engineering Course has been a demanding and tiring process. It has not been concluded yet, as the course itself is continually restructured every semester in order to incorporate new developments and students' feedback. However, so far the description of learning outcomes has been worthwhile as it proved to be helpful not only to reflect upon the course's design and activities but also to evaluate the course accordingly.

Overall, this paper advocates the use of course specific learning outcomes as various synergies may arise which may help to create better and more successful courses.

Table 2. Results of Student Self-Assessment Survey

	2014_2		2015_1		2015_2		2016_1		2016_2		Mean
	pre post	diff ttest	pre post	diff ttest	pre post	diff ttest	then post	diff ttest	then post	diff ttest	pre post
	course n = 74 pre n = 75 post n = 47		course n = 79 pre n = 78 post n = 48		course n = 66 pre n = 69 post n = 40		course n = 78 then n = 46 post n = 46		course n = 57 then n = 35 post n = 35		course n ~ 70 then n ~ 61 post n ~ 43
T1.1	3,97 4,67	0,7 <0,01	4,11 5,00	0,89 <0,01	4,59 5,13	0,53 <0,01	4,23 4,86	0,64 <0,01	4,25 4,67	0,42 0,11	4,23 4,87
T1.2	3,57 4,85	1,28 <0,01	3,71 4,84	1,13 <0,01	4,03 4,70	0,67 <0,01	3,55 4,79	1,24 <0,01	3,83 4,61	0,78 0,01	3,74 4,76
T2.1	4,20 4,79	0,58 <0,01	4,10 4,90	0,8 <0,01	4,62 4,87	0,25 0,14	3,91 4,95	1,04 <0,01	4,00 5,08	1,08 <0,01	4,17 4,92
T2.2	3,22 4,47	1,24 <0,01	3,82 4,62	0,8 <0,01	4,09 4,60	0,51 0,01	3,70 5,07	1,36 <0,01	3,78 4,78	1,00 <0,01	3,72 4,71
T3.1	4,20 4,76	0,56 <0,01	4,09 4,76	0,67 <0,01	4,32 4,83	0,51 0,01	4,20 4,70	0,49 0,02	4,23 4,72	0,49 <0,01	4,21 4,75
T4.1	3,80 4,32	0,52 <0,01	3,57 4,62	1,05 <0,01	4,03 4,63	0,6 <0,01	3,73 4,30	0,57 <0,01	3,56 4,00	0,44 0,09	3,74 4,37
C1.1	3,79 4,54	0,76 <0,01	3,82 4,76	0,94 <0,01	4,33 4,98	0,64 <0,01	4,09 4,68	0,59 0,01	4,09 4,91	0,83 <0,01	4,02 4,77
C2.1	3,79 4,36	0,57 <0,01	3,81 4,70	0,89 <0,01	4,32 4,60	0,28 0,11	4,02 4,56	0,54 <0,01	4,00 4,58	0,58 <0,01	3,99 4,56
C3.1	4,33 4,89	0,56 <0,01	4,16 4,86	0,69 <0,01	4,50 4,70	0,2 0,27	3,95 4,57	0,61 0,01	3,56 4,44	0,89 <0,01	4,1 4,69
C4.1	3,71 4,60	0,89 <0,01	3,58 4,82	1,24 <0,01	3,95 4,69	0,74 <0,01	4,05 4,59	0,54 0,03	4,06 4,64	0,58 0,02	3,87 4,67
C4.2	3,55 4,51	0,96 <0,01	3,32 4,40	1,08 <0,01	4,01 4,45	0,44 0,04	3,98 4,52	0,55 0,01	4,15 4,69	0,54 0,02	3,8 4,51
A1.1	4,05 4,72	0,67 <0,01	4,18 4,85	0,68 <0,01	4,55 5,00	0,45 0,01	3,72 4,70	0,98 <0,01	4,09 4,92	0,83 <0,01	4,12 4,84
A1.2	4,33 4,89	0,56 <0,01	4,24 5,02	0,78 <0,01	4,43 4,75	0,32 0,12	4,41 4,98	0,57 0,01	4,42 4,83	0,41 0,07	4,37 4,89
A2.1	4,34 5,09	0,74 <0,01	4,32 5,02	0,70 <0,01	4,75 4,95	0,2 0,33	4,52 5,05	0,52 0,01	4,14 4,61	0,47 0,04	4,42 4,94
A3.1	3,76 4,51	0,75 <0,01	3,67 4,71	1,04 <0,01	4,29 4,78	0,49 0,02	4,34 4,80	0,45 0,01	4,08 4,44	0,36 0,07	4,03 4,65
A4.1	-	-	-	-	4,13 4,54	0,41 0,04	3,86 4,60	0,74 <0,01	3,89 4,65	0,76 0,01	3,96 4,6

Figure 1. Heat Chart.

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